

PANDORA

Advancing Trustworthy AI in 2026

NEWSLETTER

The first months of 2026 have marked another important chapter for the PANDORA project. Building on the strong foundations established throughout 2024 and 2025, the consortium continues to advance trustworthy, efficient, and sustainable AI across the cloud-edge continuum.

From organizing international scientific workshops and contributing to major European events, to publishing impactful research on Edge AI, autonomous systems, cybersecurity, and AI deployment, PANDORA remains committed to fostering innovation while addressing the challenges of trustworthy Artificial Intelligence.

Here's a look at our latest highlights.

NEWS

AIoT Workshop at COMSNETS 2026

PANDORA

COMSNETS 2026

PANDORA PROUDLY HOSTS A SUCCESSFUL AIOT WORKSHOP AT COMSNETS, FOSTERING INNOVATION AND COLLABORATION AT THE INTERSECTION OF AI AND IOT.

2026 JANUARY 6 - 10

PANDORA successfully organized the **AIoT Workshop** at **COMSNETS 2026** in Bangalore, India, bringing together researchers and practitioners working at the intersection of Artificial Intelligence and the Internet of Things.

The workshop featured cutting-edge research on emerging AIoT methodologies, practical applications, and future challenges, encouraging lively discussions and new collaborations within the research community.

As the main organizer, PANDORA proudly contributed to strengthening international scientific cooperation and promoting innovation in AIoT technologies.

[More Details](#)

EVENTS

Plenary Meeting – Bratislava

Plenary Meeting

Exploring data pipelines, AI strategies, and impact creation through cross-partner collaboration and technical exchange.

12 - 13 Feb, 2026

PANDORA

On **12–13 February 2026**, the PANDORA consortium gathered in Bratislava, Slovakia, for its Plenary Meeting, hosted by the Slovak University of Technology in Bratislava (STU). During two intensive days, project partners reviewed overall progress, aligned technical activities, and coordinated next steps towards implementation and validation of PANDORA's trustworthy AI framework.

Highlights included: **Integration Planning** across technical work packages · **AIoT Technologies** discussions on AI orchestration, runtime architecture and data

pipelines · **Use Cases & Datasets** review across all five industrial pilots · **Dissemination & Exploitation** sessions on long-term sustainability.

ADRA Future Ready 2026

On **16 April 2026**, PANDORA participated in **ADRA Future Ready 2026** in Brussels, one of Europe's leading events on Artificial Intelligence, Data, and Robotics. As part of the **HORIZON-CL4-2023-HUMAN-01-01** project cluster, PANDORA joined EXTRA-BRAIN, MANOLO, AI-DAPT, and RAIDO to showcase the collective achievements of the cluster.

The joint presentation highlighted how the five projects address the entire AI lifecycle — from trustworthy datasets and data quality to AI models, cloud-edge infrastructures, AI operations, and reliable deployment. Discussions emphasized trustworthy datasets, cloud-edge AI pipelines, data observability, privacy-preserving technologies, ethical AI governance, and compliance with the **European AI Act**.

Data Week 2026 – Oslo

The poster for the Data Week 2026 Oslo session features a blue background with a white diamond shape on the left containing the event logo. The logo includes the text: **DATAWEEK**, JOIN. LEARN. SHARE. GET VALUE, **DATA FJORDS: UNLOCKING AI FOR INDUSTRY & SOCIETY**, and 5-6 May 2026 / Oslo. To the right of the logo, the session title is **When Data Pipelines Decide AI Trust and Efficiency: theory and practice**, with the date and time **5 May / 16:00-17:00 EEST / Room H3**. Below the title, there are eight circular portraits of speakers arranged in two rows of four. Each portrait is accompanied by the speaker's name and affiliation. The speakers are: Nuria DE LAMA (IDC), Maria PATERAKI (NTUA), Konstantinos TSERPES (ICCS-NTUA), Christos VASILAKIS (Metamind Innovations MINDS), Carlos AGOSTINHO (Uninova), Julia PALMA (CeADAR), and Pawel Herman (KTH). At the bottom of the poster, there are logos for the organizing and supporting organizations: **ORGANISED BY BDV BIG DATA VALUE ASSOCIATION**, **SUPPORTED BY The Research Council of Norway**, and **IN COLLABORATION WITH IFE SINTEF** and **NTNU VESTLANDSFORSKING**.

PANDORA participated in **Data Week 2026** in Oslo, leading the session: *"When Data Pipelines Decide AI Trust and Efficiency: Theory and Practice."*

Together with projects from the *Efficient Trustworthy AI – Making the Best of Data* portfolio, the session explored the critical role of data pipelines in enabling trustworthy and efficient AI systems, covering: data pipeline modernization, AI-ready and synthetic data, data governance and quality, and industrial pilot

experiences. Representatives from PANDORA, TURING, RAIDO, AI-DAPT, MANOLO, and EXTRA-BRAIN shared practical insights.

Online Workshop: The EU AI Act and EU-Funded Research Projects

On **7 May 2026**, PANDORA co-organized an online workshop together with the **SYNAPSE**, **CONSENTIS**, and **CURIUM** projects, focused on: *"The EU AI Act and EU-Funded Research Projects: Implications, Challenges, and Good Practices."*

Experts discussed how the evolving European regulatory landscape — including AI governance, risk classification, compliance, and data protection — will shape the development and deployment of AI systems in EU-funded research initiatives.

[Watch the recording →](#)

RESEARCH & PUBLICATIONS

Published in The Conversation

Edge AI: Bringing Intelligence Beyond the Cloud

Dr. Georgios Bouloukakis explores how Edge AI reduces latency, improves privacy, and enables efficient AI processing closer to where data is generated — and how PANDORA orchestrates resources across the IoT-Edge-Cloud continuum.

[Read article →](#)

SEAMS 2026

CRAFTER: Causality-based Self-Adaptation for Autonomous IoT Systems

Houssam Hajj, Ajay Kattepur, Denis Conan, Georgios Bouloukakis

An automated framework combining causal reasoning with reinforcement learning for self-adaptation in dynamic IoT environments, improving resilience and adaptive system optimization.

[Read paper →](#)

IEEE ICC 2026

Arena: Evaluating AI Deployment Across the Computing Continuum

A Kubernetes-based testbed for realistic evaluation of application deployment across the IoT-Edge-Cloud continuum, enabling container-based node emulation, network condition simulation, and comprehensive monitoring.

[Read paper →](#)

ACM SAC 2026

CIAK-CP: Camera Feed Injection Attack in Collaborative Perception

Calipari Marco, Fabian Maximilian Schmidt, Steinhorst Sebastian, Hamad Mohammad

A novel attack targeting collaborative perception systems in Connected Autonomous Vehicles, contributing to improving security and resilience of next-generation intelligent transportation systems.

[Read paper →](#)

VehicleSec 2026

Perspective-Shift Attacks Against Optical Perception Sensors: A Novel Attack Vector on LiDAR and Camera

Marco Calipari, Michael Kühr, Dominik Kulmer, Maximilian Luedecke, Mohammad Hamad, Sebastian Steinhorst

New attack vectors against optical perception sensors with mechanisms to detect and mitigate threats, contributing to more secure autonomous mobility.

[Read paper →](#)

Looking Ahead

As PANDORA continues its journey, the consortium remains committed to advancing trustworthy, efficient, and sustainable AI technologies through cutting-edge research, international collaboration, and active engagement with the European research community.

Stay tuned for more exciting developments as we continue shaping the future of AI across the cloud-edge continuum.

[Visit pandora-heu.eu →](https://pandora-heu.eu)

[Unsubscribe](#) | [Manage your subscription](#) | [View online](#)

This project has received funding from the EUROPEAN COMMUNICATIONS NETWORKS, CONTENT and TECHNOLOGY (CNECT) program under Grant Agreement No 101135775 (PANDORA project). This document reflects only the author's view and the European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.